

A STUDY OF MENTAL HEALTH OF PROFESSIONAL COLLEGE STUDENTS IN MADURAI DISTRICT

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Cite This Article: Dr. M. Thirumalaichamy, "A Study of Mental Health of Professional College Students in Madurai District", International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology, Volume 2, Issue 2, Page Number 134-137,

2017.

Abstract:

The study examined the mental health of professional college students. The sample of the study consisted of 300 professional college students 187 were boys and 113 were girls studying in I.T.I, Diploma and B.E. in Madurai District, Tamilnadu. Data was collected with the help of Mental Health Inventory by Peter Becker (1987). There results of the study indicated that professional college students samples such as gender, location of institution, nature of institution, professional degree, parental occupation, type of family and no of siblings do not differ significantly towards mental health and parental qualification differ significantly towards mental health of professional college students.

Introduction:

Mental Health is the capacity of each and all of us to feel, think and act in ways that enhance our ability to enjoy life and deal with the challenges we face. It is a 4 positive sense of emotional and spiritual well-being that respects the importance of culture, equity, social justice, interconnections and personal dignity. Mental health describes a level of psychological well-being, or an absence of a mental disorder. From the perspective of positive psychology or holism, mental health may include an individual's ability to enjoy life, and create a balance between life activities and efforts to achieve psychological resilience. Mental health can also be defined as an expression of emotions, and as signifying a successful adaptation to a range of demands.

The World Health Organization (2013) defines mental health as a state of wellbeing in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to his or her community. It was previously stated that there was no one official definition of mental health. Cultural differences, subjective assessments, and competing professional of all affect how "mental health" is defined.

There are different types of mental health problems, some of which are common, such as depression and anxiety disorders, and some not so common, such as schizophrenia and bipolar disorder. Kitchner, BA & Jorm, AF (2002).

"Good mental health is more than the absence of mental illness; it is a positive sense of well-being. For children and young people, it is the ability to learn, play, enjoy friendships and relationships, and deal with difficulties experienced during childhood, adolescence and early adulthood. Normally, a child's well-being is the result of healthy individual development within a sympathetic, nurturing environment. In the early years of life, infants make emotional attachments and form the first relationships that lay the foundations for future mental health.

As the child grows, his or her emotional, cognitive and social development is nurtured by good relationships with family, peers and community. The mentally healthy child should emerge from this with a clear sense of identity and self-worth, the ability to recognize and manage emotions, problem-solving and communication skills, motivation and a respect for the feelings of others.

Magotra (1982) conducted a study on the topic, Mental Health as a correlate of intelligence, Education, Academic Achievement and Socio-economic Status. He reported that (1) girls appeared to possess better mental health, were capable effacing the realities around them and were in a position to tide over the mental disequilibrium, (2) the mental health of boys and girls appear to be considerably influenced by the two factors, namely, intelligence and physical health, (3) the mental life of boys were dominated by the feelings of depression and neurotic behavior. On the other hand, girls were found to be suffering from a sense of insecurity and anxiety.

Need for the Present Study:

- ✓ Mental health is essential for the well-being and functioning of individuals.
- ✓ Good mental health is an important resource for individuals, families, communities, and nations.
- ✓ Mental health, as an indivisible part of general health, contributes to the functions of society, and has an effect on overall productivity.
- ✓ Mental health concerns everyone as it is generated in our everyday lives in homes, schools, workplaces, and in leisure activities.
- ✓ Positive mental health contributes to the social, human, and economic capital of every society.

- ✓ Spirituality can make a significant contribution to mental health promotion and mental health influences spiritual life (Underwood-Gordon, 1999).

Method of Investigation:

The present study deals with the analyses of mental health of professional college students with different systems namely, Government, Private and Aided.

Variables:

The variables chosen in the present study are mental health of professional college students

Population and Sample Characteristics:

The target population for the present study is the students in different categories of college following different systems of education at the Government, Private and Aided. From the target population a sample of 300 professional college students was chosen for the present study. The chosen sample comprised of 102 from government, 121 private and 77 from aided professional college from the government, aided and private schools were selected to study.

Research Tool Used:

- ✓ The research tools used for the present study to analyze the Mental Health by Peter Beckar (1987)

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To find out the t significant difference between the social maturity with respect to gender, location of institution, nature of institution, professional degree, parental qualification, parental occupation, type of family and no of siblings of professional college students.

Hypotheses of the Study:

- ✓ There will be no significant difference between social maturity with respect to gender, location of institution, nature of institution, professional degree, parental qualification, parental occupation, type of family and no of siblings of professional college students.

Analyses and Interpretation of Data:

Table 1: 't' Test Values For Mental Health Scores – Based on Gender

Sub-Samples	N	Mean	S.D	't' Value
Male	187	41.49	4.92	0.704 ^{NS}
Female	113	41.89	4.56	

Table 1 further reveals the mean, standard deviation and 't' values of male and female higher secondary students on mental health. The calculated 't' value is 0.704, which is lower than the table value of 1.97 to be significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the research hypothesis is rejected and null hypothesis is accepted. Further it is found that the male and female professional college students do not differ significantly in their mental health.

Table 2: 't' Test Values for Mental Health Scores –Based on Location of Institution

Sub-Samples	N	Mean	S.D	't' Value
Rural	141	42.00	4.71	1.216 ^{NS}
Urban	159	41.32	4.84	

Table 2 further reveals the mean, standard deviation and 't' values of rural and urban professional college students on mental health. The calculated 't' value is 1.216, which is lower than the table value of 1.97 to be significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the research hypothesis is rejected and null hypothesis is accepted. Further it is found that the rural and urban professional college students do not differ significantly in their mental health.

Table 3: 'F' Test Values for Mental Health Scores – Based on Nature of Institution

Nature of Institution	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	DF	'F' Value
Between Groups	7.123	3.561	2	0.154 ^{NS}
Within Groups	6847.714	23.056	297	
Total	6854.837		299	

Table 3 the calculated 'F' value is 0.154, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of nature of institution with respect to their mental health of professional college students.

Table 4: 't' Test Values for Mental Health Scores –Based on Professional Degree

Professional Degree	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	Df	'F' Value
Between Groups	45.876	22.938	2	1.001 ^{NS}
Within Groups	6808.961	22.926	297	
Total	6854.837		299	

Table 4 the calculated 'F' value is 1.001, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of professional degree with respect to their mental health of professional college students.

Table 5: 't' Test Values for Mental Health Scores –Based on Parental Qualification

Sub-Samples	N	Mean	S.D	't' Value
School Education	193	41.23	4.94	1.977 ^S
College Education	107	42.37	4.41	

Table 5 further reveals the mean, standard deviation and 't' values of whose parental qualification school education and college education of parents of professional college students on mental health. The calculated 't' value is 1.977, which is higher than the table value of 1.97 to be significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the research hypothesis is accepted and null hypothesis is rejected. Further it is found that whose parental qualification school education and college education differ significantly in their mental health.

Table 6: 't' Test Values for Mental Health Scores –Based on Parental Occupation

Sub-Samples	N	Mean	S.D	't' Value
Self Employ	160	41.80	4.71	0.605 ^{NS}
Government Employ	140	41.46	4.88	

Table 6 further reveals the mean, standard deviation and 't' values of whose parental occupation self employ and government employ of parents of professional college students on mental health. The calculated 't' value is 0.605, which is lesser than the table value of 1.97 to be significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the research hypothesis is rejected and null hypothesis is accepted. Further it is found that whose parental occupation of self employ and government employ do not differ significantly in their mental health.

Table 7: 't' Test Values for Mental Health Scores –Based on Type of Family

Sub-Samples	N	Mean	S.D	't' Value
Nuclear	149	41.20	4.92	1.568 ^{NS}
Joint	151	42.07	4.62	

Table 7 further reveals the mean, standard deviation and 't' values of whose type of family nuclear and joint of professional college students on mental health. The calculated 't' value is 1.568, which is lower than the table value of 1.97 to be significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the research hypothesis is rejected and null hypothesis is accepted. Further it is found that the type of family nuclear and joint do not differ significantly in their mental health.

Table 8: 'F' Test Values for Mental Health Scores –Based on No of Siblings

Type of Management	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	Df	'F' Value
Between Groups	150.168	75.084	2	3.326 ^{NS}
Within Groups	6704.669	22.575	297	
Total	6854.837		299	

Table 8 the calculated 'F' value is 3.326, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of no of siblings with respect to their mental health of professional college students.

Major Findings of the Study:

- ✓ It is found that the male and female professional college students do not differ significantly in their mental health.
- ✓ It is found that the rural and urban professional college students do not differ significantly in their mental health.
- ✓ There is no significant difference among sub samples of nature of institution with respect to their mental health of professional college students.
- ✓ There is no significant difference among sub samples of professional degree with respect to their mental health of professional college students.
- ✓ It is found that whose parental qualification school education and college education differ significantly in their mental health.
- ✓ It is found that whose parental occupation of self employ and government employ do not differ significantly in their mental health.
- ✓ It is found that the type of family nuclear and joint do not differ significantly in their mental health.
- ✓ There is no significant difference among sub samples of no of siblings with respect to their mental health of professional college students.

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